

Practice Abstracts

batch 1

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LiveSeeding - Organic seed and plant breeding to accelerate sustainable and diverse food systems in Europe is a 4-year Innovation Action funded by the European Union, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). The project started in October 2022 and brings together 37 organisations operating in 16 European countries. LiveSeeding provides science-based evidence and best practice solutions to help achieve 100 % organic seed.

*LiveSeeding contributes to the transition towards environmentally-friendly, climate-neutral, healthy and fair food systems through a **PUSH-PULL-ENABLE** strategy to*

- enhance the availability and adequacy of organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PUSH),
- increase and stabilise the market demand for organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PULL),
- foster an enabling policy and regulatory environment where both demand and supply can harmoniously and productively negotiate without irrelevant constraints due to legal restrictions and/or regulatory fragmentation (ENABLE).

LiveSeeding addresses the topics in a **holistic multi-actor, multi-stakeholder, participatory approach** involving stakeholders along the value chain in 17 local **Living Labs** (LLs) and 3 established networks of organic breeders (**ECO-PB**), seed savers (**ECLLD**) and Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (**MUFPP**). 15 European countries cover the different pedoclimatic zones and socio-economic contexts, including countries with a low level of development in organic seed and breeding in East and South Europe.

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	3
List of Figures	3
Summary	5
1. Introduction to practice abstracts	6
2. LiveSeeding Practice Abstracts	7
2.1 EUROPEAN ROUTER DATABASE: CENTRALISED PLATFORM FOR SUPPLIERS OF ORGANIC PLANT REPRODUCTIVE MATERIAL (PRM)	8
2.2 WHAT IS ORGANIC HETEROGENEOUS MATERIAL (OHM) AND HOW CAN IT BE NOTIFIED? 10	
2.3 SIMPLE, NON-DESTRUCTIVE MEASUREMENT OF EQUILIBRIUM RELATIVE HUMIDITY TO EVALUATE SEED MOISTURE LEVELS USING A HYGROMETER	12
2.4 ENHANCING ORGANIC VARIETY DEVELOPMENT WITH SEEDLINKED: A COLLABORATIVE DIGITAL APPROACH	14
2.5 DIY HOT WATER TREATMENT FOR SANITIZATION OF VEGETABLE SEEDS	15
3. Conclusion	17
Table of Annex	18

List of Figures

Figure 1 Scheme of European Router Database	9
Figure 2 The variability of EPO durum spikes	11
Figure 3 eRH measurement of the corander seed sample	13
Figure 4 Test hot water treatment in diagnostic laboratory	16

List of abbreviations

ECLLD	European Coordination Let's Liberate Diversity
ECO-PB	European Consortium for Organic Plant Breeding
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
EU CAP Network	EU Common Agricultural Policy Network
FiBL-CH	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture, Switzerland
FiBL-DE	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture, Germany
ITAB	Institut Technique de l'Agriculture Biologique (Technical Institute for Organic Agriculture)
KIS	Agricultural Institute of Slovenia
LLs	Living Labs
MUFPP	Milan Urban Food Policy Pact
OHM	Organic Heterogeneous Material
OMKI	Hungarian Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
ORC	Organic Research Centre
PGR	Plant Genetic Resources
PRM	Plant Reproductive Material
SERI	Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation

Summary

This deliverable provides a compilation of five practice abstracts prepared in the scope of the LiveSeeding project until month 24 (September 2024). Practice abstracts are prepared as part of Task 7.1 (T7.1), "Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan and its implementation."

Practice abstracts part of Deliverable 7.5 are:

- 1) European Router Database: centralised platform for suppliers of organic plant reproductive material (PRM)*
- 2) What is organic heterogeneous material (OHM), and how can it be notified?*
- 3) Simple, non-destructive measurement of equilibrium Relative Humidity to evaluate seed moisture levels using a hygrometer*
- 4) Enhancing Organic Variety Development with SeedLinked: A Collaborative Digital Approach*
- 5) Hot Water Treatments to Sanitize Vegetable Seeds*

They are presented in two ways:

- Plain text together with graphic elements in non-layouted format for easy copy and paste*
- A printscreen of a layouted version the Practice Abstract from the Canva editor to show what the PA will look in the EIP portal.*

During the project lifespan, a minimum of 15 practice abstracts will be delivered, feeding into two deliverables – Deliverable 7.5 (D7.5) "Practice Abstracts - batch 1 (contains five practice abstracts)" due by month 24 (September 2024) and Deliverable 7.7 (D7.7) "Practice Abstracts - batch 2 (contains ten practice abstracts)" due by month 48 (September 2026).

Practice abstracts will ensure the broad dissemination of the innovative knowledge resulting from the LiveSeeding project, which will feed into the EIP-AGRI (The Agricultural European Innovation Partnership) project database on the EU CAP Network [website](#). The end-user material is designed to convey readily accessible information to practitioners in the form of summaries for practitioners in the EIP standard format.

All practice abstracts produced in the scope of the LiveSeeding project will be deposited on the Organic Farm Knowledge platform under the section "[Seed](#)" which promotes the exchange of knowledge among farmers, farm advisers and scientists.

1. Introduction to practice abstracts

Practice abstracts are concise summaries of research findings designed to be easily understood and applied by non-specialist audiences. The practice abstracts aim to transfer complex scientific information into practical insights that can be directly used by different end users (e.g. practitioners, policymakers, and the public) and to ensure that research outcomes are accessible, relevant, and impactful beyond the academic community. These end-user materials not only highlight the key results of a project and explain how these findings can be implemented in real-world contexts, but also contribute to the sustainability and exploitation of research results. By summarizing key findings in a way that is easy to use and implement, they ensure that the knowledge generated by the project can be utilized long after the project's completion, providing a sense of security to stakeholders.

A practice abstract typically consists of four key elements that guide its core structure: the objective(s), the result(s), the recommendations, and additional information.

The "Objective" section identifies the specific issue or challenges that the research addresses, clarifying its relevance to practitioners. In contrast, the "Result" section then presents the main findings or innovations from the research that offer a solution to the identified problem. Following this, the "Recommendations" section provides actionable advice, or steps practitioners can implement to apply the solution in their contexts. Finally, the "Additional information" section includes additional resources or references for those interested in exploring the topic in more detail, such as booklets, videos, publications, etc.

The present deliverable collects 5 out of 15 practice abstracts produced/to be produced in the scope of the LiveSeeding project. It aims to ensure that all produced end-user materials are comprehensively included and easily accessible in one unified document.

2. LiveSeeding Practice Abstracts

The present deliverable collects 5 out of 15 practice abstracts planned within the scope of the LiveSeeding project. It aims to ensure that all produced end-user materials are comprehensively included and easily accessible in one unified document.

These practice abstracts are:

- 1) European Router Database: centralised platform for suppliers of organic plant reproductive material (PRM)**
- 2) What is organic heterogeneous material (OHM), and how can it be notified?**
- 3) Simple, non-destructive measurement of equilibrium Relative Humidity to evaluate seed moisture levels using a hygrometer**
- 4) Enhancing Organic Variety Development with SeedLinked: A Collaborative Digital Approach**
- 5) Hot Water Treatments to Sanitize Vegetable Seeds**

All practice abstracts are presented in two ways:

- Plain text together with graphic elements in non-layouted format for easy copy and paste
- A printscreen of a layouted version the Practice Abstract from the Canva editor to show what the PA will look in the EIP portal.

2.1 European Router Database: centralised platform for suppliers of organic plant reproductive material (PRM)

OBJECTIVE

Regulation 2018/848 requires every EU Member State to have a national database displaying the available organic plant reproductive material (PRM). However, suppliers often offering PRM across borders may need to navigate 27 different national databases, each in varying formats and languages. This poses significant challenges for suppliers and hinders the completeness of these databases.

RESULT

The European Router Database serves as a centralised platform, enabling suppliers to manage their PRM offers across multiple national databases with a single account. The platform provides translated content in all official EU languages and facilitates direct communication with national authorities. Integration of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) automates the transfer of PRM offers to national databases, with 12 APIs currently operational. For other databases, offers can be downloaded manually by authorities, widening access of organic PRM for organic farmers in their national database. To increase transparency, the Router Database will serve as a central repository where information of interest to all stakeholders can be uploaded on an ongoing basis. The use of the Router Database is free of charge both for suppliers and authorities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To place offers in national databases via the Router Database, suppliers can follow these 5 practical steps:

1. Visit the Router Database at www.seeds4organic.eu
2. Create your user account and verify your organic certification
3. Select the countries where you intend to offer your PRM
4. Place your offers by searching the cultivar catalogue and filling-in the offer form
5. Keep your offer up to date

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

For more information and support, consult our FAQs: <https://www.seeds4organic.eu/page/show?page=e7671ef8-622d-9ade-9a75-f559b46ca977>

Figure 1 Scheme of European Router Database

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2.2 What is organic heterogeneous material (OHM) and how can it be notified?

OBJECTIVE

Climate changes threaten crop production year by year, as multiple abiotic and biotic stresses affect plants simultaneously and more frequently. Moreover, the current system for regulating newly developed plant varieties is designed for uniform varieties (i.e., homogeneous plant materials), which hinders the diversification of agricultural crop production. And yet genetic and crop diversity are key elements to the resilience of systems to climatic hazards. Beside this, the breeding process itself is a time- and resource-intensive and costly process, just like the registration of the new varieties.

RESULT

One way of solving this is to use organic heterogeneous materials (OHM), which are described as a group of plants of a species that share common phenotypic characteristics but also have a high degree of genetic and phenotypic diversity (heterogeneity), dynamic evolution and adaptation to certain conditions to which DUS (distinctness, uniformity and stability) protocols are not applicable according to the (EU) Organic Regulation 2018/848. The OHM is neither a variety nor a mixture of varieties and is, therefore, not an object of the variety register but can be notified in a simpler procedure.

As a new possibility offered by the organic regulation, (organic) farmers are not yet properly informed about OHM and their notification procedure, which hinders the uptake and development of this type of cultivar. It is important to promote the OHM simplified notification procedure to the breeders, farmers, and seed producers, which will enable their marketing, foster agrobiodiversity, and provide farmers with a valuable tool to tackle the challenges of climate change. The notification of OHM is a much faster, simpler and cheaper procedure than the variety registration.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR NOTIFYING AN OHM:

The following information must be provided to the relevant competent authority of each Member State:

- a) contact details of the applicant;
- b) the species and denomination of the organic heterogeneous material;
- c) description of the parental material used for breeding, the breeding methods, process, description of the main agronomic and phenotypic properties, as well as the results of the available tests (if any), and the country of cultivation;
- d) the applicant's declaration that the information in points a), b) and c) are true; and
- e) a representative sample must also be provided.

The application must be sent by a registered letter with receipt of delivery, or via another communication channel accepted by the competent authorities – with official confirmation of delivery.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Videos

Three OHM webinars were organized by LiveSeeding project partners (ÖMKi and F & Z Dottenfelderhof). Presentations can be found on the YouTube channel: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLccjPZoqxq7RP5rKz5RbvPCT_kniDxerG

Organic Heterogeneous Material: new marketing regime for diversified seed populations (by Seeds4All and Artemisia AIBSL) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BDkomih6oWY>

Booklets

Participatory breeding in the XXI. Century (English and Hungarian). EN version: <https://biokutatas.hu/upload/inline/2022%20reszveteli%20nemesites%20en%20v4.pdf>

HU version: <https://biokutatas.hu/hu/webshop/item/123/reszveteli-nemesites-a-xxi-szazadban>

OHM - A new marketing regime for diversified seed populations https://opensourceeds.org/sites/default/files/bilder/BLOG/OHM_LLD_Booklet_S4A.pdf

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Figure 2 The variability of EPO durum spikes

2.3 Simple, non-destructive measurement of equilibrium Relative Humidity to evaluate seed moisture levels using a hygrometer

OBJECTIVE

For an optimal shelf life of seeds, it is crucial that seeds are dry enough. A method still widely used to measure moisture levels is to determine the proportion of water in the fresh weight, expressed in %, also known as moisture content. This method involves oven-drying the sample and weighing the seeds before and after, which is destructive and rather labour-intensive. Another inconvenience is that the recommended water content depends on the seed oil content and varies between 4 and 9%.

RESULT

Equilibrium relative humidity (eRH) is an alternative measure of the seed moisture level, also expressed in %. It can be measured by placing the seeds in an airtight container together with a hygrometer. The RH of the air will reach an equilibrium, being the eRH, which reflects the moisture level of the non-oil part of the seeds and is thus independent of the oil content. An eRH of around 30% is considered optimal for seed conservation. This method is non-destructive, requires less labour and is independent of the oil content of the seeds.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Material: an airtight container (glass jar or hermetic box) and a hygrometer

Protocol

- Place seeds in the airtight container.
- Add the hygrometer and close the container. Make sure you can read the hygrometer through the container or lid when closed, except if it is a digital hygrometer that can be read remotely.
- Place the container in the storage room at storage temperature.
- Check the hygrometer regularly and wait until the RH is stable. The fuller the container the faster the equilibrium is reached. Usually, eRH is reached within 24 hours, or even within a few hours.
- If eRH is higher than 35%, it is recommended to dry the seeds further.
- Keep in mind that commercial hygrometers often have an accuracy of +/- 2%

If you are measuring the eRH of a seed sample, make sure that in the meantime the rest of the seed lot is stored under stable conditions or in an air-tight container. Otherwise, your sample might no longer be representative of your seed lot.

Also, keep in mind that RH varies with temperature. Thus, your eRH measurement is valid as long as temperature conditions are fairly stable.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

A Practical Guide from the LiveSeeding project provides more practical advice and background knowledge on the topic of drying and storing vegetable seeds in organic small-scale and on-farm seed production: <https://organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/52128>

The Seed Information Database (SID) is a compilation of seed biological trait data hosted by the Society for Ecological Restoration (SER). It offers an equilibrium moisture content calculator to estimate moisture content based on seed oil content, temperature and the measured eRH. The "use preset" option provides seed oil contents for several crop species. <https://ser-sid.org/viability/moisture-equilibrium>

A similar calculation tool under Excel format is available for download from the website of the supplier of Drying Beads®. This tool provides average seed oil content for some additional crop species, which are not available on the SID. http://www.dryingbeads.org/?page_id=84

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Figure 3 eRH measurement of the coriander seed sample

2.4 Enhancing Organic Variety Development with SeedLinked: A Collaborative Digital Approach

OBJECTIVE

Traditional methods of variety evaluation and on-farm cultivar testing often face significant challenges. These methods can be time-consuming, inconsistent, and typically lack a participatory approach. Farmers and researchers struggle with the complexities of collecting, analyzing, and sharing data effectively across diverse regions and languages while ensuring compliance with data protection regulations like GDPR.

RESULT

The SeedLinked platform provides a comprehensive digital solution for participatory variety evaluation and on-farm testing. Its tools for data collection, analysis, and sharing are accessible via both web and mobile apps, supporting multiple languages to ensure wide accessibility and GDPR compliance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Utilize SeedLinked for Trial Management: Take advantage of the platform's user-friendly interface and powerful tools to efficiently organize and manage variety trials.
- Engage with Educational Resources: Participate in webinars and video tutorials available on SeedLinked, designed to help first-time users navigate the platform effectively.
- Contribute Feedback for Platform Enhancement: Provide feedback based on your trial experiences to help improve the platform, ensuring it meets the specific needs of European organic variety evaluation.
- Maximize Mobile App Features: Use the mobile app for real-time data entry and image tagging to streamline fieldwork and enhance data accuracy.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

- SeedLinked Website: Visit SeedLinked for additional information.
- YouTube Channel: Check out SeedLinked Videos for tutorials and insights. Here a full tour of the platform
- Webinars and Tutorials: Available directly on the SeedLinked platform.
- Case Study: Read about the Salsify trial with ProSpecieRara for practical insights.

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2.5 DIY Hot water treatment for sanitization of vegetable seeds

OBJECTIVE

Seed-borne pathogens are of special importance to horticultural practices, especially for farmers and home gardeners as bacterial and fungal diseases, such as bacterial blights or anthracnose, can cause low germination ability, slow growth of the plants or even total loss of the yield in the case of severe infections. Regular commercial coatings with chemicals, such as fungicides or disinfectants, are not an option for organic agriculture, making the management of seed-borne pathogens especially challenging.

RESULT

Hot water treatment is a cost-effective and environmentally sustainable technique that has been successfully used in sanitation of vegetable seeds by reduction or elimination of pathogens without affecting the seeds. The method has been effectively used to manage seed borne diseases without the use of synthetic pesticides which favours even small- scale gardeners. The rationale is based on the principle of heat, wherein the right temperature and the right amount of time is given to deactivate the pathogens, with as little impact as possible on the seeds.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Hot water treatment is well suited to small seed batches, where the precise control of temperature and duration can be controlled more easily. However, the special attention has to be paid when heat-sensitive seeds are applied, such as beans and peas, because due to the soaking in hot water the seed coat can be damaged easily which would lead to a reduced germination rate. Therefore, seed-specific treatment protocols need to be followed.

Material:

- Seeds
- Stockings or fine mesh bags
- Paper clips or similar small fasteners to secure the mesh bags/stockings
- Thermometer (for monitoring water temperature)
- Glass beaker or pot for heating water
- Heating device (e.g., magnetic stirrer with a hot plate for controlled heating)
- Timer (to monitor treatment time)
- Cold water for cooling treated seeds
- Paper towels for drying seeds post-treatment

Procedure:

1. Prepare Seed Bags - Place seeds in mesh bag. Secure the open ends of the stockings with paper clips; use differently coloured clips if different seed batches are treated at the same time.
2. Heat Water to the Target Temperature – Place glass beaker or pot with water on a heating device. Using a thermometer, heat the water to the desired temperature.
3. Submerge Seeds - Once the water reaches targeted temperature, carefully place the secured seed bags into the water. Make sure they are fully submerged but not overcrowded to allow even heating.
4. Monitor Treatment Time - Set a timer for 30 minutes (or the recommended time for the specific seed type). Stir occasionally or maintain water circulation to ensure even heat distribution.
5. Cool the Seeds - After the treatment time is completed, immediately remove the seed bags and submerge them in cold tap water for 1-2 minutes to stop the heating process.
6. Dry the Seeds - Open the stockings and spread the seeds out on paper towels. Allow them to dry thoroughly before planting or storing.

Recommendations:

Plant species	Option 1	Option 2
Corn Salad, Carrots, Celery	50 °C / 30 min	53 °C / 10 min
Brassicas, Onions, Radishes	50 °C / 20 min	53 °C / 10 min
Lettuce	50 °C / 0.5 min	50 °C / 10 min
Beetroot	53 °C / 30 min	53 °C / 40 min

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

More details, tips and tricks about HWT of vegetable seeds you can find here: https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/53533/1/HotWaterTreatment_BSAG.pdf

Figure 4 Test hot water treatment in diagnostic laboratory

3. Conclusion

The five practice abstracts developed within the LiveSeeding project offer practical insights and actionable solutions for organic seed and breeding practices. These abstracts provide valuable guidance on topics such as enhancing seed quality, improving breeding strategies, and promoting sustainable agriculture practices, tailored for farmers, seed producers, and breeders.

By addressing both the challenges and opportunities within organic seed systems, the abstracts contribute to fostering innovation, increasing resilience, and supporting the growth of organic farming across Europe.

Overall, they play a crucial role in disseminating knowledge and best practices to strengthen organic seed knowledge and promote sustainable food systems.

Table of Annex

Title of the Practice Abstract	Link to the Practice Abstract
European Router Database: centralised platform for suppliers of organic plant reproductive material (PRM)	Practice Abstract no. 1
What is organic heterogeneous material (OHM), and how can it be notified?	Practice Abstract no. 2
Simple, non-destructive measurement of equilibrium Relative Humidity to evaluate seed moisture levels using a hygrometer	Practice Abstract no. 3
Enhancing Organic Variety Development with SeedLinked: A Collaborative Digital Approach	Practice Abstract no. 4
Hot Water Treatments to Sanitize Vegetable Seeds	Practice Abstract no. 5

European Router Database: centralised platform for suppliers of organic plant reproductive material (PRM)

OBJECTIVE

Regulation 2018/848 requires every EU Member State to have a national database displaying the available organic plant reproductive material (PRM). However, suppliers often offering PRM across borders may need to navigate 27 different national databases, each in varying formats and languages. This poses significant challenges for suppliers and hinders the completeness of these databases.

Figure: Scheme of European Router Database

RESULT

The European Router Database serves as a centralised platform, enabling suppliers to manage their PRM offers across multiple national databases with a single account. The platform provides translated content in all official EU languages and facilitates direct communication with national authorities. Integration of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) automates the transfer of PRM offers to national databases, with 12 APIs currently operational. For other databases, offers can be downloaded manually by authorities, widening access of organic PRM for organic farmers in their national database.

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Social Media: Facebook [[LiveSeeding](#)], X [[@LiveSeeding](#)] & LinkedIn [[LiveSeeding](#)], website [liveseeding.eu]

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and Innovation

What is organic heterogeneous material (OHM) and how can it be notified?

Figure: The variability of EPO durum spikes

OBJECTIVE

Climate changes threaten crop production year by year, as multiple abiotic and biotic stresses affect plants simultaneously and more frequently. Moreover, the current system for regulating newly developed plant varieties is designed for uniform varieties (i.e., homogeneous plant materials) which hinders the diversification of agricultural crop production. And yet genetic and crop diversity are key elements to the resilience of systems to climatic hazards. Beside this, the breeding process itself is a time- and resource-intensive and costly process, just like the registration of the new varieties.

RESULT

One way of solving this is to use organic heterogeneous materials (OHM), which are described as a group of plants of a species that share common phenotypic characteristics but also have a high degree of genetic and phenotypic diversity (heterogeneity), dynamic evolution and adaptation to certain conditions to which DUS (distinctness, uniformity and stability) protocols are not applicable according to the (EU) Organic Regulation 2018/848. The OHM is neither a variety nor a mixture of varieties and is, therefore, not an object of the variety register but can be notified in a simpler procedure.

As a new possibility offered by the organic regulation, (organic) farmers are not yet properly informed about OHM and their notification procedure, which hinders the uptake and development of this type of cultivar. It is important to promote the OHM simplified notification procedure to the breeders, farmers, and seed producers, which will enable their marketing, foster agrobiodiversity, and provide farmers with a valuable tool to tackle the challenges of climate change. The notification of OHM is a much faster, simpler and cheaper procedure than that of the variety registration

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following information must be provided to the relevant competent authority of each Member State:

- contact details of the applicant;
- the species and denomination of the organic heterogeneous material;
- description of the parental material used for breeding, the breeding methods, process, description of the main agronomic and phenotypic properties, as well as the results of the available tests (if any), and the country of cultivation;
- the applicant's declaration that the information in points a), b) and c) are true; and
- a representative sample must also be provided.

The application must be sent by a registered letter with receipt of delivery, or via another communication channel accepted by the competent authorities – with official confirmation of delivery.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

- OHM webinars - Presentations on the YouTube channel: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLccjPZqoxq7RP5rKz5RbvPCT_kniDxerG
- Organic Heterogeneous Material: new marketing regime for diversified seed populations (by Seeds4All and Artemisia AIBSL) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BDkomih6oWY>
- Participatory breeding in the XXI. Century (English and Hungarian). EN version: <https://biokutatas.hu/upload/inline/2022%20reszveteli%20nemesites%20en%20v4.pdf>; HU version: <https://biokutatas.hu/hu/webshop/item/123/reszveteli-nemesites-a-xxi-szazadban>
- OHM - A new marketing regime for diversified seed populations https://opensourceseeds.org/sites/default/files/bilder/BLOG/OHM_LLD_Boklet_S4A.pdf

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LiveSeeding: Organic seed and plant breeding to accelerate sustainable and diverse food systems in Europe. Horizon Innovation Actions 2022 - 2026.

Social Media: Facebook [LiveSeeding], X [@LiveSeeding] & LinkedIn [LiveSeeding], website [liveseeding.eu]

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UK Research
and Innovation

Simple, non-destructive measurement of equilibrium Relative Humidity to evaluate seed moisture levels using a hygrometer

Figure: eRH measurement of a sample of coriander seeds in a 350ml glass jar with a rubber seal. The jar was filled to the top before inserting a hygrometer (bought in the terrarium section of a pet shop) just under the lid

OBJECTIVE

For an optimal shelf life of seeds, it is crucial that seeds are dry enough. A method still widely used to measure moisture levels is to determine the proportion of water in the fresh weight, expressed in %, also known as moisture content. This method involves oven-drying the sample and weighing the seeds before and after, which is destructive and rather labour-intensive. Another inconvenience is that the recommended water content depends on the seed oil content and varies between 4 and 9%.

RESULT

Equilibrium relative humidity (eRH) is an alternative measure of the seed moisture level, also expressed in %. It can be measured by placing the seeds in an airtight container together with a hygrometer. The RH of the air will reach an equilibrium, being the eRH, which reflects the moisture level of the non-oil part of the seeds and is thus independent of the oil content. An eRH of around 30% is considered optimal for seed conservation. This method is non-destructive, requires less labour and is independent of the oil content of the seeds.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Material

- an airtight container (glass jar or hermetic box) and a hygrometer

Protocol

- Place seeds in the airtight container
- Add the hygrometer and close the container. Make sure you can read the hygrometer through the container or lid when closed, except if it is a digital hygrometer that can be read remotely.
- Place the container in the storage room at storage temperature
- Check the hygrometer regularly and wait until the RH is stable. The fuller the container the faster the equilibrium is reached. Usually, eRH is reached within 24 hours, or even within a few hours.
- If eRH is higher than 35%, it is recommended to dry the seeds further.
- Keep in mind that commercial hygrometers often have an accuracy of +/- 2%.

If you are measuring the eRH of a seed sample, make sure that in the meantime the rest of the seed lot is stored under stable conditions or in an air-tight container. Otherwise, your sample might no longer be representative of your seed lot. Also, keep in mind that RH varies with temperature. Thus, your eRH measurement is valid as long as temperature conditions are fairly stable.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

- A Practical Guide from the LiveSeeding project provides more practical advice and background knowledge on the topic of drying and storing vegetable seeds in organic small-scale and on-farm seed production: <https://organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/52128>
- The Seed Information Database (SID) is a compilation of seed biological trait data hosted by the Society for Ecological Restoration (SER). It offers an equilibrium moisture content calculator to estimate moisture content based on seed oil content, temperature and the measured eRH. The "use preset" option provides seed oil contents for several crop species. <https://ser.sid.org/viability/moisture-equilibrium>
- A similar calculation tool in Excel format is available for download from the website of the supplier of Drying Beads®. This tool provides average seed oil content for some additional crop species, which are not available on the SID. http://www.dryingbeads.org/?page_id=84

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UK Research
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Enhancing Organic Variety Development with SeedLinked: A Collaborative Digital Approach

OBJECTIVE

Traditional methods of variety evaluation and on-farm cultivar testing often face significant challenges. These methods can be time-consuming, inconsistent, and typically lack a participatory approach. Farmers and researchers struggle with the complexities of collecting, analyzing, and sharing data effectively across diverse regions and languages while ensuring compliance with data protection regulations like GDPR.

Figure: Homepage of the SeedLinked platform

RESULT

The SeedLinked platform provides a comprehensive digital solution for participatory variety evaluation and on-farm testing. Its tools for data collection, analysis, and sharing are accessible via both web and mobile apps, supporting multiple languages to ensure wide accessibility and GDPR compliance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Utilize SeedLinked for Trial Management: Take advantage of the platform's user-friendly interface and powerful tools to efficiently organize and manage variety trials.
2. Engage with Educational Resources: Participate in webinars and video tutorials available on SeedLinked, designed to help first-time users navigate the platform effectively.
3. Contribute Feedback for Platform Enhancement: Provide feedback based on your trial experiences to help improve the platform, ensuring it meets the specific needs of European organic variety evaluation.
4. Maximize Mobile App Features: Use the mobile app for real-time data entry and image tagging to streamline fieldwork and enhance data accuracy.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

- SeedLinked Website: Visit [SeedLinked](#) for more information.
- YouTube Channel: Check out [SeedLinked](#) Videos for tutorials and insights. [Here](#) is a full tour of the platform
- Webinars and Tutorials: Available directly on the SeedLinked platform.
- Case Study: Read about the Salsify trial with ProSpecieRara for practical insights.

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DIY Hot water treatment for sanitization of vegetable seeds

Figure: Test hot water treatment at diagnostic laboratory

OBJECTIVE

Seed-borne pathogens are of special importance to horticultural practices especially for farmers and home gardeners as bacterial and fungal diseases such as bacterial blights or anthracnose, can cause low germination ability, slow growth of the plants or even total loss of the yield in the case of severe infections. Regular commercial coatings with chemicals, such as fungicides or disinfectants, are not an option for organic agriculture making the management of seed-borne pathogens especially challenging.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Hot water treatment is well suited to small seed batches, where the precise control of temperature and duration can be controlled more easily. However, the special attention has to be paid when heat-sensitive seeds are applied such as beans and peas, because due to the soaking in hot water the seed coat can be damaged easily which would lead to reduced germination rate. Therefore, seed-specific treatment protocols need to be followed.

Material:

- Seeds
- Stockings or fine mesh bags
- Paper clips or similar small fasteners to secure the mesh bags/stockings
- Thermometer (for monitoring water temperature)
- Glass beaker or pot for heating water
- Heating device (e.g., magnetic stirrer with a hot plate for controlled heating)
- Timer (to monitor treatment time)
- Cold water for cooling treated seeds
- Paper towels for drying seeds post-treatment

Procedure:

1. Prepare Seed Bags - Place seeds in mesh bag. Secure the open ends of the stockings with paper clips; use differently colored clips if different seed batches are treated at the same time
2. Heat Water to the Target Temperature - place glass beaker or pot with water on a heating device. Using a thermometer, heat the water to the desired temperature
3. Submerge Seeds - once the water reaches targeted temperature, carefully place the secured seed bags into the water. Make sure they are fully submerged but not overcrowded to allow even heating.
4. Monitor Treatment Time - Set a timer for 30 minutes (or the recommended time for the specific seed type). Stir occasionally or maintain water circulation to ensure even heat distribution.
5. Cool the Seeds - after the treatment time is completed, immediately remove the seed bags and submerge them in cold tap water for 1-2 minutes to stop the heating process.
6. Dry the Seeds - open the stockings and spread the seeds out on paper towels. Allow them to dry thoroughly before planting or storing.

RESULT

Hot water treatment is a cost-effective and environmentally sustainable technique that has been successfully used in sanitation of vegetable seeds by reduction or elimination of pathogens without affecting the seeds. The method has been effectively used to manage seed borne diseases without the use of synthetic pesticides which favors even small scale gardeners. The rationale is based on the principle of heat, wherein the right temperature and the right amount of time is given to deactivate the pathogens, with as little impact as possible on the seeds.

Recommendations:

Plant species	Option 1	Option 2
Corn Salad, Carrots, Celery	50 °C/30min	53 °C/10min
Brassicas, Onions, radishes	50 °C/20min	53 °C/10min
Lettuce	50 °C/5min	50 °C/10min
Beetroot	53 °C/30min	50 °C/10min

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

More details, tips and tricks about HWT of vegetable seeds you can find here:
https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/53533/1/HotWaterTreatment_BSAG.pdf

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